

Firm Profitability and Working Capital Policies: An Investigation of Commercial Banks of Pakistan

Kainaat, Adnan Ahmad, Kamil Zada, Afshan Afsar, Salman Zeb, Muhammad Ilyas

Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: August 21, 2020</p> <p>Accepted: December 12, 2020</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords Working Capital Management, Aggressive/Conservative Working Capital Investment Policies, Aggressive/Conservative Working Capital Financial Policies, Commercial Banks.</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.7013695</p>	<p><i>The present study examines the impact of working capital management practices on profitability of commercial banks listed in Pakistan Stock Exchange. We argue that since working capital management is a function of firm performance in non-financial firms based on earlier studies, we premise that the same theory holds true for financial firms also. We use data from 2015-2020 for 25 banks of Pakistan that are listed on Pakistan Stock Exchange. We use panel data and secondary data has been obtained from the sample banks' websites, Pakistan Stock Exchange, and State Bank of Pakistan. For firm performance, we use return on assets and return on equity as proxies for profitability while current assets to total assets ratio is used for working capital investment policy and current liabilities to total assets ratio are used for working capital financing policy, respectively. Firm size, debt ratio, and current ratios are used as control variables. Using regression analysis, we find that the sample banks use conservative working capital investment policy and aggressive working capital financing policy. We show that both these proxies have a positive association with firm performance while the control variables, as theorized, show negative relation with firm performance. This study has implications for not only banks but also for policy makers that banks tend to opt for less current assets than other firms. This study is limited to the use of a sample of financial institutions with limited dataset, however, future research may include more broader sample of all financial institutions with a large dataset to investigate the association for more robust results.</i></p>

1. Introduction

The current worldwide financial emergency and the insolvencies of numerous associations like General Motors, Bear Stearns, Lehman Brothers, among others, conveyed an important message to business firms the significance of managing organizational resources, and particularly working capital management (Weston et al., 1977). Such important decision, as they refer to it, is the management of working capital. Working capital (WC) is the difference between current assets and current obligations (Ahmad, 2015). It addresses firm association in current resources such as cash, stock, attractive protections, and receivables etc. WC administration is characterized as a choice about transient supporting and assessing to take care of the connection between the firm's current assets and current obligations (Weston et al., 1977). As such managers define and identify three main policies linked to working capital management.

1. Aggressive
 2. Conservative, and
 3. Moderate
1. Aggressive working capital financing strategy suggests that current liabilities are kept up with in a more noteworthy piece when contrasted with long term obligations since current payouts bear less pace of interest and cause more reserve funds. While aggressive investment strategy suggests that elevated degrees of fixed assets and low investment in current resources might create more benefits for a firm however bear a gamble of lacking assets for everyday tasks and for installment of short-term obligations.
 2. In conservative working capital financing strategy, a more prominent piece of long-term debt is utilized as opposed to current liabilities. While conservative investment strategy is inverse to it with less interest in fixed resources and more in current resources.
 3. Moderate strategy keeps up with harmony between current resources and current liabilities. It suggests that current resources ought to be funded with current liabilities while fixed resources ought to be supported by long term liabilities (Zadeh et al., 2011).

If a firm adopts an aggressive working capital management investment policy, they keep their current assets at lower level in percentage of total assets. In case of aggressive working capital management financing policy,

firms keep their current liabilities at higher level in percentage of total liabilities where higher level of current assets have negative impact on profitability of firms, but lower level of current assets may cause interruption in daily operations due to lack of resources and availability of funds (Horne et al., 2004).

Conservative investment strategy and aggressive financing strategy is sound for a company because current liabilities bear low interest rate than the long-term liabilities that will be more advantageous and beneficial for company (Ahmad, 2015). Working capital investment and funding strategies are essentially different through various projects. On one hand, a firm practices aggressive investment strategy along with aggressive financing approach while on the other hand a firm's conservative investment policy drives conservative financing (Filbeck et al., 2005).

The impact of working capital management on profitability cannot be avoided because the survival of a firm depends upon the improvement in the profitability of the firm. It is important to know the impact of working capital on profitability of the firm to make sound decision on working capital. Sound managed working capital makes sure to sustain liquidity to services its debts, pay its employees and paying its liabilities. Many researchers have studied working capital management (WCM) and firm profitability (FP) from different perspective and in different environments. The efficient and effective management of working capital can increase the profitability of firm. Working Capital Management is defined as "managing current assets and current liabilities". Profitability of firm increases via accurately handling their cash, inventories, and account receivables (Safdar, 2016).

Working Capital and related investment and financing strategies have been investigated throughout the world (Afza et al., 2007). For example, Nazir (2008) investigates different WC strategies and its relevant financing strategy and their effect on firm's profitability. He finds that aggressive investment and financing strategies have negative effect on firm's profitability. Moreover, there is a positive relationship between conservative investment strategy and profitability, conversely there is a negative relationship between an aggressive financial strategy and profitability and value of the company. Aggressive investment working capital strategies are more likely to follow aggressive working capital financing strategies (Nazir, 2008; Al-Mualla, 2012; Bilal, 2013).

Effective management of working capital and there polices are very important for profitability of firms. Different industries use different WCM practices and policies. These working capital practices and policies themselves change significantly within industries through time (Filbeck et al., 2005). The effective management of liquidity includes planning and controlling of current assets and current liabilities in such a way that the risk of failure to meet short-term obligations is reduced and to avoid unnecessary investment in current assets. The relationship between liquidity and profitability is measured by the current ratio and its related cash gap (cash conversion cycle). The cash conversion cycle is of more importance as a measure of liquidity than the current ratio to affect profitability. There are great dissimilarities between industries with respect to the significant measure of liquidity (Eljelly, 2004).

The effect of working capital management on financial performance can be described through WC ratios. These WC ratios include inventory turnover, current ratio, quick ratio, average collection period and average payment period. Studies show that cash conversion cycles and return on assets have a significant negative relationship (Hailu, 2015). Moreover, he finds a significant negative relationship between return on assets, debt ratio and current ratio. There is a positive association between inventory turnover, sizes of sales, growth and return on assets. A significant negative association exists between return on assets, debt ratio, account payables turnover, account receivables, Cash conversion cycles and current ratio. (Abenet Yohannes Hailu, 2015, Abdul Raheman, et al., 2007).

A firm's profitability is greatly affected by the firm's WC investment policy and its financing policy. Conservative investment policy and aggressive financing policy is sound for a company since it requires a firm to invest more in current assets than fixed assets. On the other hand, in aggressive financing policy, firms keep more current liabilities than long term liabilities since current liabilities bear low interest rate than the long-term liabilities which is more advantageous and beneficial for company (Ahmad, 2015).

Studies investigate the association of liquidity with profitability of the firm, average collection period, inventory turnover in days, average payment period and cash conversion cycle (Rahman, et al., 2007; Arshad, 2013). Thus, by reducing the number of days accounts receivable and inventories to a reasonable minimum the firm managers can generate value for their shareholders (Rahman, et al., 2007). Additionally, account receivables, account payables, current ratio have significant effects on firm profitability and quick ratio has negative affect on firm profitability. More precisely long-term account receivables and inventory periods increase firm profitability, shorter account receivables and inventory period decrease firm profitability (Arshad, 2013). These studies show that firms working in such industries which follow aggressive investment working capital policies tend to practice conservative WC financing policies (Rehman, 2011).

Effective and efficient management of WC is essential for producing greater return and to maximize shareholder wealth because it helps to generate value for shareholders. Similarly, profitability is affected by WCM. For example, Shin et al., (1998) show that there is strong negative relationship among duration of a firm's net-trading cycle and profitability of a firm and smaller net trade cycles related to greater risk adjusted stock returns

(Shin et al., 1998). Thus WCM may assist only to meet short-term obligations by refining the supply chain and credit policies and increase the efficiency and improve performance, not profitability (Huy-Cuong Nguyen, 2016).

Working capital investment and financing policies are significantly variables in different industries. For example, normally it is noted and concluded that a firm with aggressive investment policy drive together an aggressive financing policy. Alternatively, firms with conservative investment policy follow conservative financing policy (Afza et al., 2007). Studies report that there is an opposite relationship between aggressive strategy of WCM and productivity of companies listed in Tehran Stock Exchange while a direct relationship is reported between conservative WCM policy and productivity of companies listed in Tehran Stock Exchange (Samadiet al., 2016). Furthermore, Mualla (2012) reports that a positive relationship between conservative investment strategy and profitability while a negative relationship between an aggressive financial strategy and profitability as well as value of the company. Using control variables, he reports that firm size, GDP growth and company growth affect profitability and value of the company positively (Al-Mualla, 2012). Padachi (2006) reports negative association between high investment in inventories and receivables with profitability and an increase in receivables and inventories decrease firm profitability. In corast he also finds that decrease in receivables and inventories increases firm profitability).

The ineffective WCM not only reduces profits but may eventually also lead to economic concerns. Thus, every company, unrelatedly of its profit formation, size, and characteristics of company, required essential amount of working capital. Therefore, the efficient management of working capital is the most critical factor in keeping liquidity, profits, solvency, and success of a company (Siddiquee et al., 2009).

Working capital is crucial for the survival of every business. It is important for running business day to day operations and is main part of business investment. It is improved profitability; retain liquidity and solvency of firm (Mukhopadhyay 2004; Krueger, 2005). There are different factors which effect WCM of a firm. Both internal and external factors are important for making WCM decisions, but internal factors are more important than external factors. It includes profitability, debt ratio and size of the company and operating cash flows of firm (Chiou et al., 2006). Commonly, in a balance sheet, current assets comprise of raw materials, cash and bank balances, account receivables, work in progress, finished goods or inventories which are short term in nature that are used for manufacture and sales, which can be transformed to cash within the year. In addition, current liabilities indicate to financial obligations which must be paid within the year or not earlier than year (Ross et al, 2010). In an efficient WCM, a manager has to make a combination of techniques and policies since these decisions are associated with the next year for the cash flow and profitability and are not taken on capital investment basis (Reason, 2008).The main objective of WCM is handling current financial resources of a firm in way to make tradeoff between profitability of firm and risk related with that profitability (Ricci et al, 2000)

Effective management of working capital is very important for the success of organization, empirical results show that failure of organization is mainly due to ineffective WCM. The aim of financial management is to decrease the level of WCand avoiding the risk of unavailability of capital for operations (Bhattacharya, 1997).Impact of WC depends on the techniques used to manage working capital such as profitability of a firm can be increased by reducing inventories, receivable turnover, net trade cycle and cash conversion cycle. Moreover, efficient management of working capital is vital for generating value for shareholders and to improve performance of firm (Wang, 2002).Higher aggressive liquidity management policy increase profitability of firm but it also increases risk. Higher the length of cash conversion cycle, the lower the profitability while profitability is increased by lowering length of cash conversion cycle (Jose et al., 1996).Practices shows that firm having higher return on assets have also higher cash balances, but it does not mean that they avoid management of working capital, they also try to minimize the negative effects and to maximize the positive effects of liquidity on profitability of firm (Czyzewski, et al., 1992).

As shown above, considerable research has been conducted to investigate the impact of WCM on profitability of firm in non-financial sectors, none of them attempted to uncover the said relationship in the context of financial sector. This study aims to fill the gap by analyzing the working capital management impact on profitability in the context of commercial banks of Pakistan.The importance of conducting this research is it will help firms' managers to develop their learning to decrease the probability of default, especially in turbulent time; in view that working capital management has impact on the profitability of firms. Additionally, this study is also has a significance for practitioners, policy makers, academicians and firm managers with regards to issue related with the effect of WCM on profitability of financial institutes, as it enables minimization of firm's cost of finance and further planning being conducted in order to maximize firm's profitability and shareholders' wealth.

2. METHODOLOGY

The study investigates the association working capital management and its relative effect on profitability of the firm. This investigation is analyzed using panel data methodology, which is a blend of cross-sectional and time-series analysis. Only listed commercial banks on Karachi Stock Exchange (KSE) are selected for this research and their secondary data has been taken from published reports of commercial banks, from website of State Bank of Pakistan.

2.1 Sample and population

We use a sample of 20 commercial banks listed on Pakistan Stock Exchange Pakistan. We selected the sample for the research from this population to check the impact of working capital on profitability of these financial institutes. Sample is selected through simple random sampling technique because it is useful technique since it gives equal chances of selection to all sample observations and avoids sampling error (Castillo, 2009). The banks with inaccessible or missing data were excluded and the banks which are liquidated during the selected time-period are also excluded. Time period of study is from 2015 to 2020. Working capital management can be measured with the help of their components which are current ratio (CR), current assets to total assets ratio (CATAR), current liabilities to total assets ratio (CLTAR), cash conversion cycles (CCC), and debt ratio (DR). Financial performance of a firm can be measured with the help of return on invested capital (ROIC), return on assets (ROA) and Tobin's Q (TQ) (Mohamad et al., 2010).

2.2 Econometric model

$$FP = \beta_0 + \beta_1 (CATA_{it}) + \beta_2 (CLTA_{it}) + \beta_3 (CR_{it}) + \beta_4 (SOF_{it}) + \beta_5 (DR_{it}) + u_{it}$$

Where FP is firm performance; CATA is current assets to total assets; CLTA is current liabilities to total assets; CR is current ratio; SOF is size of bank; and DR is debt ratio.

2.3 Variables

This research is based on the premise that WCM play an important role in firm profitability particularly on commercial banks as sample. To investigate this association, the above variables are proposed to be used in the study. The details and definition (measurement) of these variables are given in the following paras.

2.3.1. Dependent Variable

We use Return on assets (ROA) and Return on Equity as our dependent variables. ROA is a proportion which makes sense of how effectively a firm is using its current assets for the boost of benefits. Expansion in ROA normally shows an expansion in profitability while Return on Equity shows how a firm is using the shareholders' investment in generating returns (Gitman, 2002).

$$ROA = (\text{Earnings before interest and taxes} / \text{Total Assets}) \times 100$$

$$ROE = (\text{Earnings before interest and taxes} / \text{Total Outstanding Shares}) \times 100$$

2.3.2 Independent Variables

Current Assets to Total Assets Ratio (CATA) is used to discover the investment strategy of working capital embraced by the organizations under consideration. It is estimated through the following formula.

$$CATA = \text{Total current assets} / \text{Total assets}$$

A low value of Current assets to total assets ratio exhibits an aggressive investment strategy while a low value represents conservative investment strategy. This variable is used since others argue that CATA emphatically affects benefit (Ahmad et al., 2015; Mohamad et al., 2010; Afza et al., 2008; Rahman et al., 2010; and Haq et al., 2011).

$$CLTA = \text{Current liabilities} / \text{Total Assets}$$

Current Liabilities to Total Assets Ratio (CLTA) is utilized to find the working capital financing strategy. A higher value of current liabilities to total assets ratio shows more aggressive financing strategy as well as the other way around. Ahmad et al. (2015), Saad et al. (2010), Nazir et al. (2008) and Rahman et al. (2010) report that CLTA adversely affects profitability of firm.

$$CR = \text{Current Assets} / \text{Current liabilities}$$

Current Ratio (CR) measures the capacity of a firm having enough resources to cover its short-term commitments, i.e., to estimate the liquidity of firm. Higher ratio represents higher liquidity and vice versa. Shah et al. (2005), Amir et al. (2006), and Bhunia and Brahma (2011) conclude that CR adversely affects profitability of firm.

Control variables:

To examine the effect of WCM on the profitability of firms, various investigations have integrated the utilization of different variables which influence their association with profitability. These variables are based on earlier studies which report that these variables affect the firms' profitability (Shah et al., 2005; Amir et al., 2006; and Bhunia & Brahma, 2011). In this research we propose to use two control variables.

Debt Ratio (DR) is extent of firm total assets supported by debt/ creditors. It addresses the leverage of a firm. It can be calculated by:

$$\text{Debt Ratio (DR)} = \text{Total Liabilities} / \text{Total Assets}$$

Mohamad et al. (2010), Gill et al. (2010), Raheman and Nasr (2007), Ching et al. (2011) and Raheman et al. (2010) they concluded that DR has adverse consequence on profitability of firm. Therefore, in this study expected impact on profitability is negative.

Size of firm (SOF)

It is measured as **Natural log of Total Assets**. Rahman and Nasr (2007), Padachi (2006) and Rahman et al. (2010) used SOF in their study which determine that SOF positively influence profitability.

3. Results

In this study we utilized two kinds of data analysis descriptive and quantitative.

3.1 Descriptive analysis:

Descriptive analysis shows the quantity of perceptions of the multitude of variables, average value, and their standard deviation. It likewise shows the minimum and maximum values of the variables which can be achieved by these variables.

Table 1 Descriptive Statistics of Working Capital Management and Firm profitability

Variables	Mean	Med	Min	Max	Std. Dev	Skew	Kurt
ROA	1.016	1.87	.090	2.01	0.53	1.05	0.18
RoE	1.133	1.024	0.11	2.12	0.20	1.22	2.18
CLTA	1.091	2.01	.410	1.68	0.35	-0.39	-1.18
CATA	94.42	97.92	90.40	97.70	1.82	-0.21	0.61
CR	8.71	9.22	4.050	23.45	3.81	-0.59	-0.98
DR	92.16	90.31	81.49	94.83	3.15	-0.27	-0.88
SOF	19.35	21.22	17.62	20.55	0.86	0.26	-0.44

Table 1 shows descriptive statistics of all the variables sample Pakistani commercial banks for the period of 2015 to 2020. The mean value of return on assets (ROA) is 1.015 and standard deviation is 0.53. Minimum and maximum values for the firm profitability is 0.90 and 2.01 while that for RoE is 0.11 and 2.12. All the values for the rest of the variables for skewness and kurtosis show that all variables are normally distributed. Firm profitability shows that on average, all commercial banks for Pakistan provide a good return to its investors. Worth for ROA is 2.0100 while minimum worth is 0.09. The WCM policies adopted by the sample banks show lower values of its related variables, i.e., Current liabilities to total assets (CLTA) mean value is 1.091 and std. deviation is 0.35; Current assets to total assets (CATA) mean value is 94.42 and std. deviation is 1.82 with a maximum value of 97.7 and minimum value is 90.4. For liquidity, the selected sampled commercial banks Current ratio (CR) is used with a mean value of 8.71 and std. deviation is 3.81. The minimum value is 4.05 while maximum value is 23.45. Debt financing (leverage) of these commercial banks show a mean value of 92.16 and std. deviation is 3.15; maximum value is 94.83 while minimum value is 81.49. All these values show that the variables proposed to use in the study are normally distributed.

3.2 Regression Analysis

This section provides results for regression analysis. We proposed that firm profitability is a function of working capital management besides other factors. We proposed an econometric model in Section 2.2, wherein we have included independent variables with control variables. We present our results for the analysis in the following section.

Table 2: Regression Results of Firm Profitability with Working Capital Management

Variables	Dependent Variable = RoA			Dependent Variable = RoE		
	Coefficients	t-statistics	p-values	Coefficients	t-statistics	p-values
(Constant)	-10.689	-2.383	.024	-9.22	-2.97	0.020
CATA	0.110	2.951	.006	0.230	2.983	0.005
CLTA	-0.343	-1.200	.240	-0.434	-1.751	0.251
CR	-0.018	-.795	.433	-0.18	-1.200	0.240
DR	-0.082	-1.866	.072	-0.062	-0.951	0.343
SOF	0.488	4.757	.000	0.481	4.866	0.000
Adjusted R-Squared	= 53.2%			Adjusted R-Squared = 45.4%		
F-Statistics	= 34.99***			F-Statistics = 29.99***		

Table 2 shows simple linear regression of all the variables of Sample Pakistani commercial banks for the time-period 2015-2020. We show that results for most of the variables are in line with our expectations that we proposed during the literature review. We find that current assets to total assets (CATA) have a positive association with FP (both RoA and RoE) and this association is statistically significant ($p\text{-value} \leq 0.05$). This means that commercial banks in Pakistan follow an aggressive policy for WCM. Our results are consistent with other studies of Mohammad et al. (2010), Afza et al. (2008), Rahman et al. (2010), and Haq et al. (2011). Current liabilities to total assets (CLTA) have a negative relation with RoA and RoE with an insignificant statistical level. Thus, we are unable to draw robust conclusion. Our results are in line with other studies of Saad et al. (2010), Nazir et al. (2008) and Rahman et al. (2010). Current ratio (CR) has a negative connotation with both firm profitability measures and the association is not statistically significant which again portray an inconclusive argumentation of what sort of policies are being followed by the sample commercial banks with respect to WCM. However, our results are consistent with other studies in the area such as Shah et al. (2005), Amir et al. (2006), Bhunia and Brahma (2011), and Afza et al. (2008).

Regarding control variables, we find that Debt ratio (DR) is weakly statistically significant at 10% level with firm profitability (i.e., ROA and RoE). These results are in line with prior research of Mohamad et al. (2010),

Gill et al. (2010), Rahman and Nasr (2007), Ching et al. (2011) and Rahman et al. (2010). Size of firm (SOF) is strongly significant at the level of 1%. SOF has significant and positive relation with ROA and RoE. It concluded that 1 unit change in SOF cause same change in ROA and RoE, if SOF increase it increase FP and vice versa. Our results are in line with Rahman and Nasr (2007), Padachi (2006), Rahman and Nasr (2007), and Rahman et al. (2010). Table 2 also shows model summary which demonstrates that general model is statistically significant. The adjusted R-Squared for RoA is 53.2% and for RoE is 45.4%, respectively.

5. CONCLUSION

This research proposed to investigate the association of firm profitability with working capital management. We premise that working capital management is an important managerial decision to determine whether the firm is following which policy of working capital i.e., to show whether the sample follows aggressive working capital management or conservative working capital management. We investigate to determine that effective management of working capital is most vital for profitability of commercial banks sector. In order to determine what sort of policies the sample follow, we take a sample from the commercial banks of Pakistan for the period 2015-2020. Using regression model, the results show that Aggressive/conservative working capital strategies have significant impact on commercial bank's profitability. Aggressiveness of working capital management strategies has inverse relation with profitability with a negative impact on profitability while conservative investment strategy and conservative financing strategy have a direct positive relation with profitability. It implies that the organizations apply conservative investment strategy wherein they invest less in fixed resources and greater investment in current resources. These sample banks use conservative financing strategy which is better in the sense that these organizations keep up with additional long liabilities as contrast with current liabilities, thus, improves profitability. Furthermore, current ratio and debt ratio has negative impact on profitability i.e., an increase in leverage reduces profitability of these commercial banks and decrease in leverage raise profitability.

We may conclude, based on the results of the study, that bank managers can make improve the returns for their banks and investors by taking on powerful working capital management strategies. The financial managers of commercial banks ought to follow conservative investment strategy and conservative financing strategy of working capital management since the results show that they ought to focus on current assets when contrasted with fixed assets and interestingly, they utilize the long-term liabilities when contrasted with current liabilities.

In future, other researchers can extend empirical model such is increase in number of variables or can use other variables such is receivables turnovers, payables turnovers and other working capital variables. Moreover, a longer time-period can also be used since this study was limited to only 6 years data. They may also conduct comparative research. Additionally, they can extend the numbers of years and number of banks can also be extended. They can also select other sectors and countries for a comparative purposes since different markets have different forces acting as determinants of major policy decisions.

References

- Afza, T., & Nazir, M. S. (2007). Is it better to be aggressive or conservative in managing working capital? *Journal of quality and technology management*, 3(2), 11-21.
- Ahmad, A., & Bano, S. (2015). Working capital management matters profitability of textile sector: With GLS model. *International Journal of Economics and Empirical Research*, 3(11), 543-549.
- Ahmed, Z., Awan, M. Z., Safdar, M. Z., Hasnain, T., & Kamran, M. (2016). A Nexus between Working Capital Management and Profitability: A Case Study of Pharmaceutical Sector in Pakistan. *International Journal of Economics and Financial Issues*, 6(3S).
- Bhunia, A. (2011). Importance of liquidity management on profitability. 43.
- Bhutto, N. A., Abbas, G., ur Rehman, M., & Shah, S. M. M. (2015). Relationship of Cash Conversion Cycle with Firm Size, Working Capital Approaches and Firm's Profitability: A Case of Pakistani Industries. *Pakistan Journal of Engineering, Technology & Science*, 1(2).
- Burja, C. (2011). FACTORS INFLUENCING THE COMPANIES' PROFITABILITY. *Annales Universitatis Apulensis: Series Oeconomica*, 13(2), 215.
- Charitou, M. S., Elfani, M., & Lois, P. (2010). The effect of working capital management on firm's profitability: empirical evidence from an emerging market. *Journal of Business & Economics Research*, 8(12), 63.
- Chaudhury, S. K., & Pathi, S. N. Working Capital Management in Aluminium Sector: A Case Study of NALCO.
- Darjezi, J. I. Z., Choudhury, H., & Nazarian, A. (2017). Simulation evidence on the properties of alternative measures of working capital accruals: new evidence from the UK. *International Journal of Accounting & Information Management*, 25(4), 378-394.
- David, M. M. (2009). The influence of working capital management components on corporate profitability: A survey on Kenyan listed firm. *Research Journal of Business Management*, 3(1), 1-11.
- Eljelly, A. M. (2004). Liquidity-profitability tradeoff: An empirical investigation in an emerging market. *International journal of commerce and management*, 14(2), 48-61.

- Filbeck, G., & Krueger, T. (2005). Industry related differences in working capital management. *Mid-American Journal of Business*, 20(2), 11-18.
- Gill, A., Biger, N., & Mathur, N. (2010). The relationship between working capital management and profitability: Evidence from the United States. *Business and Economics Journal*, 10(1), 1-9.
- Gul, S., Khan, M. B., Raheman, S. U., Khan, M. T., Khan, M., & Khan, W. (2013). Working capital management and performance of SME sector. *European Journal of Business and management*, 5(1), 60-68.
- Haq, I. U., Sohail, M., Zaman, K., & Alam, Z. (2011). The relationship between working capital management and profitability: a case study of cement industry in Pakistan. *Mediterranean Journal of Social Sciences*, 2(2), 365-372.
- Islam, M. R., & Rahman, M. M. (1994). Working capital trends the selected enterprises in Bangladesh. *Rajshahi University Studies, Part-C*, 2, 25-28.
- Khan, S. U., Amir Shah, S. M., & Hijazi, S. T. (2005). Impact of working capital management on the profitability of firms: Case of listed Pakistani companies.
- Mohamad, N. E. A. B., & Saad, N. B. M. (2010). Working capital management: The effect of market valuation and profitability in Malaysia. *International Journal of Business and Management*, 5(11), 140.
- Mojtahedzadeh, V., Tabari, S., & Mosayebi, R. (2011). The Relationship between Working Capital Management and Profitability of the Companies (Case Study: Listed Companies on TSE). *International Research Journal of Finance and Economics*, 76(1), 158-166.
- Nazir, M. S., & Afza, T. (2009). Impact of aggressive working capital management policy on firms' profitability. *IUP Journal of Applied Finance*, 15(8), 19.
- Padachi, K. (2006). Trends in working capital management and its impact on firms' performance: an analysis of Mauritian small manufacturing firms. *International Review of business research papers*, 2(2), 45-58.
- Pouraghajan, A., & Emamgholipourarchi, M. (2012). Impact of working capital management on profitability and market evaluation: evidence from Tehran stock exchange. *International Journal of Business and Social Science*, 3(10).
- Raheman, A., & Nasr, M. (2007). Working capital management and profitability—case of Pakistani firms. *International review of business research papers*, 3(1), 279-300.
- Raheman, A., Afza, T., Qayyum, A., & Bodla, M. A. (2010). Working capital management and corporate performance of manufacturing sector in Pakistan. *International Research Journal of Finance and Economics*, 47(1), 156-169.
- Safiullah, K., Amir, S. M., & Syed, H. (2006). Impact of Working Capital Management on the Profitability of Firms. *Case of Listed Pakistani Companies. Journal of social sciences, AIOU, Islamabad*, 13, 41-50.
- Sathyamoorthi, C. R. (2002). Management of working capital in selected co-operatives in Botswana. *Finance India*, 16(3), 1015.
- Technological and Economic Development of Economy, 12(3), 222-226.
- Wang, Y. J. (2002). Liquidity management, operating performance, and corporate value: evidence from Japan and Taiwan. *Journal of multinational financial management*, 12(2), 159-169.
- Yunos, R. M., Nazaruddin, N., Ghapar, F. A., Ahmad, S. A., & Zakaria, N. B. (2015). Working capital management in Malaysian Government-linked companies. *Procedia Economics and Finance*, 31, 573-580.

Author Information

Kainaat

PhD Scholar, Institute of Business Studies and Leadership (IBL), Abdul Wali Khan University Mardan

Dr. Adnan Ahmad

Corresponding Author: Associate Professor, IBL, Abdul Wali Khan University Mardan

Kamil Zada

PhD Scholar, IBL, Abdul Wali Khan University Mardan

Afshan Afsar

PhD Scholar, IBL, Abdul Wali Khan University Mardan

Salman Zeb

PhD Scholar, IBL, Abdul Wali Khan University Mardan

Dr. Muhammad Ilyas

Assistant Professor IBL, Abdul Wali Khan University Mardan
